

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19151600

Perceived Influence Of Funding Models On Management Of Public Secondary Schools In Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated perceived influence of funding models on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study. Two hypotheses were formulated and teste at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,028 teachers from 43 public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone of Benue State. The sample was 257 teachers selected from 11 public secondary schools. A researcher developed questionnaire titled “Funding Models and School Management Questionnaire (FMSMQ)” was used for data collection. Data collected were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer research questions and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study were as follows; School alumni association and parents’ teachers’ association has significant perceived positive influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that funding models has significant positive perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others that the Ministry of Education should institutionalize alumni involvement by creating a national framework that mandates the registration and participation of alumni associations in school management boards. Additionally, training workshops should be organized for school administrators on how to effectively collaborate with alumni bodies for fundraising, mentorship and infrastructural support.

Keywords: funding models, school alumni association, parents’ teachers association and management.

INTRODUCTION

The management of public secondary schools has been a critical concern globally, in the United Kingdom, schools face challenges related to budget cuts and funding formula disparities, leading to constrained educational outcomes (National Audit Office, 2019). Similarly, South Africa’s public secondary schools struggle with inequitable resource distribution, resulting in inefficiencies in managing school facilities and instructional materials (Wills, 2019). In West Africa, particularly Ghana, the limited funding has been linked to the poor quality of educational services and infrastructure maintenance (Ankomah, Kwabena & Atta, 2020). Nigeria, on the other hand, has encountered persistent underfunding issues that hamper effective management, with North Central states, including Benue State, experiencing difficulties in ensuring adequate human and material resources for optimal school administration (Adeoye & Olawale, 2018). Within Benue State, the lack of sustainable funding models exacerbates problems such

as poor infrastructure, inadequate staffing, and ineffective planning and monitoring mechanisms, which undermine the overall effectiveness of public secondary school management (Ikpe, 2020).

Management is a systematic process that involves planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, and controlling human and material resources to achieve organizational goals efficiently and effectively (Koontz, Weihrich, Cannice & Koontz, 2020). It focuses on the optimal utilization of available resources through informed decision-making, leadership, and supervision to ensure that organizational objectives are realized within set constraints of time and resources. Modern views of management emphasize not only task accomplishment but also human relations, innovation, accountability, and adaptability to changing environments, making management a dynamic and continuous activity in both public and private organizations. Scholars further regard management as both an art and a science, combining technical knowledge with interpersonal skills to guide individuals and groups toward collective goals in a sustainable manner (Robbins & Coulter, 2018; Daft, 2021).

Management of public secondary schools in Benue State of Nigeria especially in Makurdi Education Zone appear to be in deplorable condition, due to challenges of financing faced by the financiers. The consequences on the school environment are so devastating, the school building are dilapidated and number and size of classrooms are so inadequate that teaching and learning cannot be enhanced. Basic school materials like libraries, laboratories, chairs, fans and vehicle among others are getting out of reach (Kpolovie & Obilo, 2013). The result is that many parents seems to have been forced to withdraw their children from public schools. The effective management of public secondary schools could be achieved if there is adequate funding.

Funding refers to the process of generating, allocating, and utilizing financial resources to support organizational activities, programmes and development objectives in order to achieve predetermined goals efficiently and sustainably (Baker & Levin, 2018). It involves mobilizing funds from diverse sources such as government allocations, private sector contributions, grants, donations and internally generated revenue, while ensuring accountability, transparency, and prudent financial management. According to Enefu, Aminu, and Ameh (2020), funding can be defined as the provision of financial resources to fulfill the requirements of a particular project or programme. These funding models can be enhanced through contributions from school alumni associations, which provide additional financial resources to support school programmes and infrastructure

A school alumni association refers to an organized body of former students of an educational institution who maintain formal ties with their alma mater in order to support its development and advancement (Owusu, 2019). Such associations function as important stakeholders in school management by contributing financial resources, mentoring current students, supporting infrastructural development and promoting the school's image within the wider society. The execution of alumni-focused projects involves developing comprehensive alumni engagement strategies that reference best practices in alumni relations and fundraising, as outlined by organizations like the Council for Advancement and Support of Education (CASE) (CASE, 2020). Successful project execution involves implementing targeted initiatives to cultivate strong relationships with alumni.

Alumni groups frequently engage in fund-raising activities to support infrastructural development in schools. These initiatives have a profound impact on enhancing the learning environment for current students. In many instances, alumni associations fund the construction and renovation of classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and sporting facilities. For example, in Nigeria, several public secondary schools have benefited from alumni donations, which have been instrumental in building modern classrooms and equipping science laboratories. Such contributions address critical infrastructural gaps, allowing schools to offer better educational services despite limited government funding (Ike, 2019). This direct financial input often alleviates the school's reliance on government allocations, leading to more efficient use of public funds for other essential needs. The school alumni associations often collaborate with the Parents-Teacher Association (PTA) to pool resources and strengthen initiatives aimed at improving school facilities and student outcomes

Parents' Teachers' Association (PTA) refers to a formal, school-based organization that brings together parents/guardians and teachers to collaborate in supporting the academic, social, and moral development

of learners as well as the effective management of schools (Epstein, 2018). It serves as a platform for shared decision-making, communication, and partnership between the home and the school, with responsibilities that often include mobilizing funds, improving school facilities, promoting discipline, and enhancing teaching and learning conditions. In Nigeria, PTA is backed by law in some states making it compulsory for parents and teachers; while in other states it is voluntary: whichever way, parents compulsorily pay levies agreed by associations for their wards' attendance in a particular school (Ugwulashi, 2012).

The Parent-Teacher Association is an association for the voluntary benefit of parents, guardians, and teachers at a certain school. To help create a supportive environment that will aid in the process of teaching and learning in schools, the Parents/Teachers Association (P.T.A.) aims to foster mutual understanding and collaboration between parents and teachers (Okeke, 2019). The main objective of any PTA is to help enrich the educational environment and learning experience of all students through parents' and teachers' involvement. PTA can engage in various activities such as providing support or input to major school events. P.T.A. seeks to provide parents with information about what is happening in the school and an opportunity to voice their opinions on matters about their children (Elui, 2017). Capital projects such as building new classrooms or administrative buildings, fencing the school, providing staff rooms, staff quarters, labs, etc. are funded by the P.T.A. According to Elui (2017), P.T.A. facilitates communication and decision-making between parents and instructors regarding the upbringing, welfare and management of students, staff, and the school. It is in charge of resolving the majority of issues that school administrators may run into to make sure that kids are appropriately prepared for learning, including extracurricular activities like intramural sports (National P.T.A., 2018).

As secondary schools face evolving challenges and growing complexities, the need for effective funding models has become increasingly apparent. Adequate and sustainable funding is essential to ensure the smooth functioning of schools, the provision of quality education, and the overall development of students. Over the years, the traditional funding mechanisms for public secondary schools have encountered various limitations. Budget constraints, resource disparities, and bureaucratic hurdles have often hindered the seamless administration of these institutions. Consequently, this has led to compromised educational standards, reduced access to essential facilities, and a decline in academic performance. Despite this situation, school principals are not sufficiently proactive in seeking alternative funding models for secondary education. Instead, they rely heavily on government subsidies, which have proven to be insufficient. By effectively tapping into various funding models like school alumni association, parents and teachers' association, community-based funding initiatives, public-private partnership and philanthropist, there is a significant potential to enhance the delivery of education in a more effective manner. Based on the above background, the researcher sought to investigate perceived influence of funding models on the management of secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

The management of public secondary schools plays a vital role in ensuring the achievement of educational goals and the effective functioning of the school system. Adequate funding is widely believed to be one of the major factors that influence the smooth administration of schools, provision of instructional materials, maintenance of infrastructure, and the overall quality of teaching and learning. In many parts of Nigeria, including Benue State, government funding alone may no longer be sufficient to meet the growing needs of public secondary schools. Consequently, other funding models such as support from school alumni associations and Parents' Teachers' Associations (PTAs) are increasingly expected to complement government efforts in the management of schools. These groups are often perceived as important stakeholders who may contribute financial resources, provide infrastructural support, and participate in decision-making processes that enhance school development.

However, despite the expected contributions of these funding sources, the management of many public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone appears to be facing numerous challenges which may be associated with inadequate or ineffective funding mechanisms. There are growing concerns that some schools may be experiencing poor infrastructural development, insufficient teaching and learning

materials, and administrative difficulties that could hinder effective school management. It could be that the contributions of school alumni associations and Parents' Teachers' Associations are not sufficiently harnessed, coordinated, or sustained to support school management effectively. This situation may be troubling as it raises questions about the extent to which these funding models actually influence the management of public secondary schools in the area. If this situation persists, it might continue to affect the efficiency of school administration and the overall quality of education delivered to students. It is against this backdrop that this study sought to investigate the perceived influence of funding models, particularly school alumni associations and Parents' Teachers' Associations, on the management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate perceived influence of funding models on the management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the perceived influence of school alumni association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.
2. evaluate the perceived influence of parents' teachers' association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. what is the perceived influence of school alumni association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria?
2. what is the perceived influence of parents' teachers' association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. School alumni association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.
2. Parents' teachers' association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,028 teachers from 43 public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone of Benue State. The sample was 257 teachers selected from 11 public secondary schools. A researcher developed questionnaire titled "Funding Models and School Management Questionnaire (FMSMQ)" was used for data collection. Data collected were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation to answer research questions and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit test at 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A total of 257 copies of questionnaire were taken to the field and administered on respondents and 250 copies representing 97% of the questionnaire was returned answered and 7 copies representing 3% were damage or lost. The data presentation, analysis and interpretation for this study were based on the responses obtained from respondents on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: *What is the perceived influence of school alumni association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Perceived Influence of School Alumni Association on Management of Public Secondary Schools

I/NO	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
1	Alumni funds are insufficient for the school's needs	83	145	09	13	3.19	0.73	Agree
2	School alumni association actively participate in decision-making processes related to school funding.	108	97	32	13	3.20	0.85	Agree
3	School alumni association contributions are insufficient to make a noticeable impact on school buildings.	94	134	09	13	3.23	0.75	Agree
4	Some school alumni are more interested in influencing school decisions than providing support.	96	132	09	13	3.03	0.85	Agree
5	School alumni members often provide scholarships to support students financially.	69	146	09	26	3.17	0.78	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation						3.17	0.78	Agree

Source: Field work 2026

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 3.19, 3.20, 3.23, 3.03 and 3.17 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.73, 0.85, 0.75, 0.85 and 0.78 respectively. The result indicates that the respondents largely agreed that alumni funds are insufficient to meet the comprehensive needs of the school, highlighting limitations in the financial impact of alumni support. The findings also reveal that school alumni associations are actively engaged in decision-making processes related to funding, suggesting their participatory role in financial planning and resource allocation. Moreover, respondents agreed that alumni contributions do not significantly improve school infrastructure, emphasizing the need for more substantial and consistent inputs. Some alumni were perceived to be more interested in influencing school decisions than providing genuine support, pointing to potential conflicts of interest or misplaced priorities. However, it was also observed that school alumni members frequently provide scholarships, indicating their commitment to supporting students' academic success. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 benchmark. The cluster mean of 3.17 was also above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that school alumni associations are perceived to have a positive influence on the management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State.

Research Question 2: What is the perceived influence of parents' and teachers' association on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Perceived Influence of Parents' and Teachers' Association on Management of Public Secondary Schools

I/NO	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
6	PTA contributions are insufficient to address the school's library needs.	110	107	20	13	3.25	0.81	Agree
7	PTA contributions enable the school to hire additional teaching staff.	113	63	61	13	3.10	0.94	Agree
8	PTA provides essential support for the school's sports and cultural activities.	114	114	09	13	3.31	0.77	Agree
9	PTA supports teachers and students by providing essential learning tools.	99	112	26	13	3.18	0.82	Agree
10	PTA focuses more on organizing events than to improve school laboratory equipment.	118	110	09	13	3.23	0.77	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation						3.23	0.80	Agree

Source: Field work 2026

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.25, 3.10, 3.31, 3.18 and 3.23 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.81, 0.94, 0.77, 0.82 and 0.77 respectively. The result indicates that the respondents largely agreed that PTA contributions are insufficient to fully meet the needs of school libraries, suggesting a gap in resource provision in this area. The responses also showed that PTA contributions have enabled schools to hire additional teaching staff, indicating their support in addressing personnel shortages. Furthermore, respondents perceived that the PTA provides vital assistance in organizing sports and cultural activities, demonstrating the association's role in promoting extracurricular development. It was also agreed that PTAs support both teachers and students by supplying necessary learning tools, reinforcing their contribution to the academic environment. However, respondents noted that PTAs tend to focus more on event organization than on improving laboratory facilities, highlighting a possible imbalance in priorities. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 benchmark. The cluster mean of 3.23 was also above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that parents' and teachers' associations are perceived to have a positive influence on the management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State.

Hypothesis 1: School alumni association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-square Test of Perceived Influence of School Alumni Association on Management of Public Secondary Schools

Response	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2	P-value	Decision
			3	0.05	490.544	.000	Sig.
SA	90	62.5					
A	131	62.5					
D	13	62.5					
SD	16	62.5					
Total	250						

Table 3 reveals that $\chi^2 = 490.544^a$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that school alumni association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies that school alumni association has significant perceived positive influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Parents' and teachers' association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of Perceived Influence of Parents' and Teachers' Association on Management of Public Secondary Schools

Response	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2	P-value	Decision
			3	0.05	565.696	.000	Sig.
SA	111	62.5					
A	101	62.5					
D	25	62.5					
SD	13	62.5					
Total	250						

Table 4 reveals that $\chi^2 = 565.696^a$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that parents' and teachers' association has no significant perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies that parents' and teachers' association has significant perceived positive influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The following discussions of findings are presented based on the results obtained from the analyses of the hypotheses:

The first finding of the study showed that school alumni association has positive significant perceived positive influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with the findings of Adoga (2024), who revealed that active involvement of school alumni associations through financial support, provision of facilities and mentorship programmes significantly enhances administrative effectiveness and overall school management in public secondary schools. The finding also agrees with the findings of Ihonde (2024), which showed that alumni associations contribute positively to school governance by supporting infrastructural development, staff welfare and policy implementation, thereby strengthening management practices in public secondary schools. The researcher agrees with this finding that school alumni associations have a positive significant perceived influence on the management of public secondary schools. This is because alumni associations often serve as strong support systems to school management by mobilising resources, sharing professional expertise and fostering accountability, which collectively improve planning, organisation and effective management of public secondary schools.

The second finding of the study revealed that Parents' Teachers' Association has significant perceived positive influence on management of public secondary schools in Makurdi Education Zone, Benue State, Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings of Iorfa (2024), who found that effective PTA involvement positively influences school management through improved communication, shared decision-making, and provision of additional resources for school development. Similarly, the finding aligns with that of Kwaghbo (2024), who reported that PTA participation enhances school management efficiency by supporting discipline, monitoring academic activities and supplementing government funding in public secondary schools. The researcher also agrees with this finding because when parents and teachers collaborate through the PTA, school management benefits from collective responsibility, increased transparency and community support, which contribute to improved administrative effectiveness and sustainable management of public secondary schools.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that diverse funding models significantly contribute to the effective management of public secondary schools in the zone. Specifically, the school alumni association and parents' teachers' association contributions were all perceived to have a positive significant influence on school management. This underscores the vital role of stakeholder involvement and alternative funding mechanisms in enhancing educational quality, promoting infrastructural development, and ensuring efficient administration in public secondary schools.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Ministry of Education should institutionalize alumni involvement by creating a national framework that mandates the registration and participation of alumni associations in school management boards. Additionally, training workshops should be organized for school administrators on how to effectively collaborate with alumni bodies for fundraising, mentorship and infrastructural support.
2. Community leaders should serve as champions in mobilizing support for PTAs by fostering mutual trust between school personnel and parents. They should also help facilitate community

forums where school needs are discussed and action plans developed for mobilizing human and material resources for school development.

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